

The Exploration of Emotion and Memory in the Design of Chinese Everyday Cooking Utensils

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Abstract

In this user-centered production age, emotion is a key factor to consider for a design company or a manufacturer to approach consumer's psychology on product choice. The multiplicity of products allows consumers to also choose other elements like the design style (the external appearance in terms of colour or form) or to see if the cultural content conveyed by the product pleases the consumer, or if the product is handy. These soft elements are a human manifestation of psychological needs. A successful product also makes the consumer feel safe, and brings positive emotion to satisfy the consumer's psychological and spiritual needs.

Nowadays in the supermarkets of China, western products are seen everywhere and they are gradually becoming an important part of Chinese daily life. It is easy to find refrigerators, electric cookers, microwaves, or gas stoves in Chinese kitchens. Speed, fast economic development, and admiration of western culture make people desire to use western products. For a time, the Chinese will overlook their emotional needs when using these objects. However, some traditional cooking utensils remain. They seem common, unfashionable or homely, but they tenaciously keep their position and are well used. The reason that they are not replaced by modern products is that they support people with totally different feelings such as familiarity, steadfastness, specific typical identity, and nostalgia.

According to the latest investigation on typical Chinese kitchens in the city, modern products are only a supplement. The mostly used tools for Chinese people are still Chinese traditional tools. Chopsticks, ceramics, cooking utensils used for frying, steaming, boiling, stirring such as an iron pan, casserole pot, steaming pot, and purple bronze pot are still used in their traditional forms. The tenacity of these traditional objects reminds us they are important for Chinese people to satisfy their needs in a deep way. More and more archaeological evidences indicate that two thousand years ago Chinese people had already been using this cooking system in a mature way. In this long history the traditional objects have not changed greatly in shape, function, or even technology. Chinese people rely a lot on common tools in use for more than two thousand years.

This paper is an exploration of how ordinary tools affect Chinese people psychologically, regarding their original form, the underlying culture dynamics and value conveyed. How Chinese people's affection for them affects their choice of production is also important. The research data examines two groups of kitchen tools, one is mostly used tools from Chinese kitchens, and the other is tools with same function as the first group but from archaeological discovery. The comparison between the two groups tries to uncover the relationship between original cooking tools and present tools, to explore how emotions are built up in thousands of years of use and how emotions continuously influence Chinese people's choice today.

A case study method is applied in this paper through the steps of observation, imagination, documentation and explanation. Two groups of data are set and studied in an historical context and contemporary situation to explore the emotional characteristics of Chinese cooking tools and their consistent influence.

Conference theme: Values and Culture

Keywords: Chinese everyday cooking utensils, emotion, meaning

The Layout of the Paper

Introduction

As the most common unit in people's homes, the kitchen is a very functional place. Not only as a place where food is prepared, processed and served, but a place of creating and experiencing. Through tools people can fulfil the task of cooking. These cooking tools not only satisfy people's basic needs, they can also reflect people's inner emotion and identification. Since Agnes Heller (1984) once claimed, everyday life is a field connected with tradition, customs, experiences, kinship and natural feeling and past. Cooking as aspect of everyday life, through design and usage of cooking utensils reveals deep connection with Chinese traditions, customs and ideologies.

However, the significance from design has often been overlooked in Chinese people's everyday life. Much scholarly literatures lead luxury object and little research of everyday cooking utensils on design has been conducted in past decades (Li liXin, 2000). To treat the kitchen utensil as a design system requires more attention.

In design, some researchers focusing on Chinese traditional tools have taken chopsticks or ceramics as a single case to interpret. However, most research discusses them as a typical cultural symbol (Chopsticks, 2006). Although scholars examine the relationship between cooking utensils and user's behaviour, the tradition and culture of thousands of years, the presence of deep emotional association and identified meanings of cooking utensils are inadequate.

The cooking utensils of thousands years ago are usually placed in museums as historical relics, which unconsciously build a distance between history with people's present experience. The concept of "ancient" and "modern" separates the elements of continuity in the development of cooking utensils. Although constant change exists - transformations of form, material, craft, manufacturing and techniques in the evolutionary progress of cooking utensils - consistent features of design style are also evident across Chinese history. In addition, there are also inadequate interpretations of cooking utensils from the aspect of the user's psychological and emotional needs.

Such gaps arouse a series of questions: what kinds of emotions are hidden in everyday common objects? Where do these emotions come from in terms of functional or psychological needs? How are these emotions shaped through form and function? What is the relationship between

emotional factors and design factors in an object? How are utility, satisfaction, history, aesthetics and emotions combined in an object?

The cooking utensil *fu* (pot) is chosen as a representative product for analysis. Through comparing archaeological discoveries in ancient China and the same product in kitchens today, the paper seeks to explore how Chinese people's emotions are established step by step in interactive experience between an user and an cooking utensils, how emotions affect how people choose products, and how emotions are developed from ancient cooking utensils thousands years until today. Through design analysis of *fu* (pot), the experiences between the user and utensils will be interpreted step by step.

Methods

In this study a qualitative approach was adopted and case studies were conducted. The cooking utensil examined in this paper is *fu* (Pot). There are four representative types of *fu* (pot) A, B, C, D in the case. The first three data were archaeological discoveries called *fu* (pot) which have been collected in Chinese museums and the last one is a present-day popular product called *Guo* (pot). The goal of the case study is to observe four examples A, B, C, and D, analyze the design, compare the features and interpret the meanings. Therefore, the steps designed to understand *fu* (pot) are observation, interaction, description and explanation.

The first and second steps were to establish a relationship with cooking utensils through observing and experiencing; the third and fourth steps were to describe and explain the design knowledge embodied in the four types of cooking utensils. The first step was observation. Through visual observing and formal analysis, size, colour, material, and texture of *fu* (pot) can be identified. The second step was interaction. Through using a *fu* (pot), it is possible to speculate its use.

The third step was description. Comparing with the first and second steps, description is a rational analysis of the design of *fu* (pot), which includes substantial analysis, formal analysis and design analysis. Substantial analysis includes the excavated time, place, size, weight, material, structure etc. Formal analysis includes form, material, colour, pattern etc. Design analysis focuses on use as revealed through form, meaning, aesthetics and design principles. The fourth step was explanation. Previous observation, interaction and description enable research questions to be clarified. In this step, explanation can be expressed through interpreting, deducting and speculating.

Case study – Fu

	A	B	C	D
Form				

Table 1

Observation

This step is to observe the designs which are shown in the following table.

Interaction

This step is to experience how to make and use the four styles of *fu* (pot).

Description

This section is divided into four parts:

- Substantial analysis on A, B, C, D is exhibited in below table the below.
- Formal analysis
- Similarity and difference
- Question

Substantial analysis is exhibited in the following table

	A	B	C	D
Form				
Period	Earlier Neolithic	Middle Neolithic	Western Han	Nowadays
Time	10000B.C.	5000-4000B.C.	206B.C-25B.C	2008A.D
Material	Clay	Terra-cotta Coarse clay mixed with sand	Iron	Stainless steel
Unearthed Place	Xianrendong Wannian County, Jiangxi Province 1962	Miaodigou Shan'an County Henan Province Yangshao Culture 1957	Yingchi County Juli City Relics of tomb of Qin and Han. Henan Province	South and North of China
Size	Diameter:23.2 cm, Height: 21cm	Caldron height: 10.9cm, Stove height 15.8c, Overall height:	Height : 23.2cm, Diameter of rim: 20.2cm, Diameter of	Width: 33.5cm Height: 9.2cm

		26cm, Diameter of rim of stove: 30.3cm	bottom: 8.5cm	
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Table 2

Formal analysis

The common cooking utensils in the Chinese kitchen are the cauldron, stoves and steamers. *Fu* (pot) A (cauldron), made of clay, is considered as the earliest properly shaped piece of pot discovered in China to date. According to its appearance, material and techniques used, archaeologists speculated that it was the earliest cooking utensils used in China Neolithic age which began about 10,000 years ago (National museum of Chinese history, 2004).

It is observed that, the shape of the *fu* (pot) is mostly rounded but in profile has a pointed bottom. Scholars (Yan Wenming, 2000) indicated that people might use a proper stand under the pot so that fire can be used for boiling. People who lived 10000 years in China use pointed bottom to make the heat spread over body of *fu*, apparently it is functional for effective boiling. At the same time, in addition to the shape of utensils, it is considered to have storing function by some archaeologists.

According to archaeological records, *fu* (pot) A was made of red pottery mixed with coarse sand fired at low temperatures; the colour was not pure, the thickness was uneven, and the inside walls were rough, which shows that the making of the *fu* (pot) was still at a primitive stage, with modelling and shaping both done by hand. However, this rough appearance of *fu* (pot) created a new way for cooking and it mainly provided people with a more varied diet boiling instead of roasting.

The next example *fu* (pot) B is a well-designed set for cooking, which combines a cauldron and stove. It is considered to be used in north China in middle of the Neolithic period and indicates that people used this kind of cooking tool commonly. At that time Chinese society was developed into farmer society. *Fu* (pot) B has short edge, flat belly, neck with a bigger pitch and tapered base. Such a design strengthens the function and helpfully matches the stove to achieve boiling.

Although the shape of *fu* (pot) C was changed with shallower curve compared to *fu* (pot) B, the main characteristic and function were continually and similarly applied. The design of

handles and new material invention – was a characteristic of the introduction of iron, which improved the efficiency by transforming heat quickly.

Fu (pot) D is a common and popular cooking tool which is called *Guo* in present-day China and it is largely manufactured and used in the North and South of China. The traditional material iron continues to be used, but new materials such as stainless steel and aluminium, have also been applied and are substituted for iron. However, the World Health Organization (WHO) recently appealed to people to use traditional iron pots more, because the low quality of stainless steel and aluminium pots which have excessive amounts of chromium content, could destroy people's health when they are over-heated (Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia 2008).

Similarities and differences

Compared with the four types of *fu* (pot) A, B, C, D, pottery *fu* (pot) in the Neolithic period, bronze *fu* (pot) in the Shang and Zhou periods, iron *fu* (pot) in Qin and Han dynasty, and stainless steel *Guo* (pots) today, two main characteristics can be generalized. The first is that these four *fu* (pot) have similar forms and functions. Another is that the material has constantly changed in different history periods.

Specifically, the similarity of *fu* (pot) A, B, C, D can be shown in the form of round pointed bottoms and the function of cook food. Though the form has subtle changes in the proportion of size, the design of neck, belly and the handle, the main form has not shifted much. As for function, the change is also apparent. From earliest boiling and storage functions, *fu* (pot) has extended its function to steaming and frying. Contrasting with the various cooking patterns the pot has, in the long eight thousands years of the evolution, the design concept of *fu* (pot) and patterns of use are still simple and have continuity.

Questions

The above similarities and differences lead to a question: why have the form and function of *fu* (pot) been maintained over such a long period? People usually agree that the general principle of the function of a product should evolve from simple to complex. Mihaly Csikszentmihaly indicated, “from the history of musical instruments, weapons or vehicles, that it is easy to see the evolutionary process tending toward greater and greater complexity of function” (P21,1993).

However, could this theory be applied to the case *fu* (pot)? How to explain the design consistency which exists in above four types of *fu* (pot) A, B, C, D?

Explanation

This section is divided into three parts:

- Interpretation
- Deduction
- Speculation

Interpretation (Design analysis)

Looking through the design of the *fu* (pot) from the functional aspect, the main features can be found as a shape with pointed bottom, round mouth, thin wall, shallow belly and handle.

Analyzing the main features layer by layer, this section tries to explain the user's interaction with the object from three aspects, sensory experiences, using experience and philosophical concept.

- Sensory perception (Aesthetics and meaning)

Firstly, about form, what kind of sensations do people get from the form design? What psychological response does a user have towards such a design and how does the form shape Chinese aesthetics? Based on Chinese reflection on nature in history, Chinese people think that the form derived from nature is most beautiful; a belief embodied in Chinese aesthetics which can be traced in the origins of utensils. Archaeologists insist that the origin of shape of utensils came from natural plants such as gourds, which was a special old plant in China. This shape represents Chinese perception of form coming from nature, which influences the consequent creation of objects. Gourds as naturally-born utensils affect the form design of *fu* (pot).

On this basis, the round mouth of the utensil can satisfy people's need of 'putting more things in'. At the earlier stage of the Neolithic period, people faced crucial survival challenges, their living mostly depended on if they had enough food. In such a situation, a round shape gave them the sense of 'plenty of food'. In Chinese primary ritual object design, a round shape was commonly used and it was an important design element. This sense of form gradually shaped a common concept that round means "unlimited, perfect, plenty, rich, success", which provided people psychological satisfaction.

- Using experience (design principles)

Secondly, besides getting sensations from the form of *fu* (pot), users also sensed the cooking utensils according to personal cooking experience. The design of form provides the possibility of interaction. The design of big round surfaces (mouth) provides enough space for users to observe and check the food in the cooking process easily. While a user uses his (her) personal cooking techniques for cooking, they can observe it, smell it, taste it and make the food. He (she) can use chopsticks or ladles (maybe at the time just small twigs) to help control food; also they can adjust the heating temperature. The interaction between user and cooking tool *fu* (pot) create a personal using experience and personal technology become one part of experience.

Another aspect of form is that the design of a tapered bottom is to allow heating to spread over the whole area, with the design of the wall shifting from thick to thin to make heat spread quickly. Also, a shallow belly design benefits the observation of the food in the pot. All of these design ideas are integrated into a simple shape which helps users to adapt easily. This is why the *fu* (pot) was designed to have a simple space for user to practise instead of limiting users. For Chinese people, overloaded design on tools might limit user's cooking techniques and creation. The best design is that the tool can give users space to use and the tool can be well matched with human hand and body, which means user and tools are compatible with each other into a perfect degree. There are main principles in the design of the *fu* (pot), which shapes users' personal using experience. This means the quality of the *fu* (pot) is fashioned by two important Chinese design principles, simplicity and adaptation.

- Philosophical influence

Does the shape of a simple form have psychological meaning for Chinese users? The psychological satisfaction can be supported by Chinese ancient philosophy. The principle of space design of utensils was precisely explained by Laotze in the Spring and Autumn period. In chapter 11 of *Tao Te Jing*, Laotze indicated the radical function and purpose of utensil 'Qi', which is emptiness creating space for use: "Thirty spokes unite around the nave; from their not-being (loss of their individuality) Arises the utility of the wheel. Mould clay into a vessel; from its not- being (in the vessel's hollow) arise the utility of the vessel. Cut out doors and windows in the house (wall), from their not-being (empty space) arises the utility of the house. Therefore by the existence of things we are served." (Lin Yutang, 1958)

Laotze's philosophy of "the utility of emptiness" generalized the wisdom of Chinese ancient people and has influenced the consequent Chinese design of utensils and tools. He uses normal things - vessels, vehicles and houses to explain his theory that makes objects benefit people, using emptiness (empty space or non-existence) for utility. This design concept also demonstrates why Chinese people use the basic round shape in design.

To summarize, all of these sensory experiences, using experience and philosophical concepts of the form and function of utensil *fu* (pot) result in Chinese people having strong accumulated sensations and perceptions of objects, which finally become one of the reasons for the form continually to be used for thousands of years in China.

Deduction

Based on the result of design analysis on the case of *fu* (pot), it is reasonable to state that users' identification of an object (or tool) is shaped by four stages of experiences: sensory engagement, practical engagement, environment engagement and everyday life engagement. All of these sensations produce perceptions and finally shape the meaning of an object.

User's first perception comes from sensory engagement on an object. This knowledge can be traced back to Aristotle (384-322B.C.) who designated the five senses (sight, hearing, touch, smell, taste) as the foundation of perception. When a user faces an object, they usually touch it and feel its texture and lift it to know it. It means that they received a "integrated sensation" while they see, hear, touch, smell, taste and feel an object. This means that the "integrated sensation" is established by the nature of an object, including shape, weight, material (which comes by touching), temperature, etc.

The second is practical engagement. The sensation of an object is inseparable from practical experiences. Psychologist Hermann Helmholtz indicated that perception was a two-step process: the basis is sensations, whose quality and intensity are inborn and conditioned by the specific characteristics of the sensory organs. These sensations are signs that take on meaning only through association (experiences) over the course of human development (Berdek, 2005). Through practical experience a user can identify if the design of an object can help him achieve a task. For example, in the case of *fu* (pot), only when a user uses object can they experience if the design of *fu* (pot), such as the space of emptiness, the round shape, the simple pattern and the natural material, matches their cooking technique. Through design user can observe the

colour, feel the temperature, smell and taste the food in the *fu* (pot). As Zhuangtze argued, the function of the object on this sense needs to be well matched with user's techniques to create harmony. Users, object and technique combined are for one purpose.

The third is environment engagement. All of engagements such as sensory engagement, experience involvement, emotional arousing happen in the environment. American psychologist James J. Gibson (1973, 1982) defines the environment on an ecological level, comprising surrounding, objects, events and also other living beings, which are perceived in their interactions. Perception itself is defined as an activity oriented toward developing one's own consciousness about environment and developing one's self within it" (p303, Berdek, 2005). There are two kinds of environment, one is family and another is collective group. The former is a physical kitchen space which creates space for use, the latter, group or community share common belief and culture of using experience. Both of internal (family) environment and external (community) environment affect the user's sensory perception, experience perception and emotions on object.

The fourth is everyday life engagement. Not only do the above three engagements happen in environmental contexts, they also happen in people's repetitive everyday life. Agnes Heller (1984) address everyday life in various given modes of categorization and repetitive praxis; everyday life is a field connected with tradition, customs, experiences, kinship and natural feeling and past as the basis; Therefore, everyday life provides people with familiarity, safety, intimacy and feeling of a home, strengthening people's perceptions of tools.

Speculation- Emotion establishment

Based on the observation, interaction, description and the theory foundation, the section speculation tries to provide an answer to the question raised in the previous part. Why have the form and function of certain objects been maintained through thousands years of Chinese history? How can we explain the design consistency which exists in the above four examples of *fu* (pot)? The extended questions are, where do these emotions come from, from functional, aesthetic or psychological needs? How are these emotions shaped through the form and function of design? How can utility, satisfaction, history, aesthetics, and emotions be combined in an object? Below is a speculation which tries to use psychological theory to explain the above questions.

Meaning of objects

Sensation and perception

According to archaeologist's explanation, we can imagine that, when people use cooking tools for cooking: their brain recognizes the sensation and directs their hands to hold the tools to use. Their brain automatically interprets the information it received from the hands as they touch the tool and responds to its sensation. The seemingly simple act of using the tool actually has two complex and virtually inseparable processes: sensation and perception. The brain gives meaning to sensation through perception. Perception is the process of organizing and interpreting sensory information to give objects meaning (Laura A. King, 2008). The two processes of sensation and perception are essentially inseparable in everyday life. The brain automatically perceives the information it received from the sense organs and as unified information - processing system gives objects meaning (Goldstein, 2007).

Memory

Memory also has a role of shaping meaningful experiences in everyday life, which includes meaningful events in life and things people experienced in life. Psychologists define memory as the retention of information or experience over time and memory occurs through three important processes: encoding, storage, and retrieval (p284, Laura; A. King 2008). Through memory, people weave the past into present, take information and store it or represent it and retrieve it for a later purpose. Fergus Craik and Robert Lockhart (1972) proposed a model of levels of processing which refers the idea that encoding occurs on a continuum from shallow to deep, with deeper processing producing better memory:

- Shallow level: the sensory or physical features of stimuli are analyzed.
- Intermediate level: the stimulus is recognized and given a label
- Deepest level: information is processed semantically, in terms of its meaning. At the deepest level we make associations. The more associations we make, the deeper the processing (Ragland & others, 2006; Laura, 2008)

Social group culture

Social identity refers to the way used for define ourselves in terms of our group membership (Deaux, 2001). Individuals have a common memory with group members, thus they share the meaning of objects which shape a using culture finally. A person's social identity might include identifying with a religious group, a country, a social organization, a political party, and many other groups (Carney & others, 2007; Haslam & Teicher, 2006) These diverse forms of social

identity reflect the numerous ways people connect to groups and social categories (Abrams & Hogg, 2004; Hong & Abrams, 2007; Postmes & Jetten, 2006). Social psychologist Kay Deaux (2001) identified five distinct types of social identity: ethnic and religious, political, vocations and avocations, personal relationships, and stigmatized groups (p468, Laura, 2008).

According to the above evidence, the meaning of an object is established by sensations and perceptions, memory, and social group culture. Through everyday cooking activities, a user participates in the sensation of cooking utensils, repetitive labour, related family gathering (events), and atmosphere in internal environment. These entire experiences and constant perceptions arouse his (her) emotions on objects and environments. The accumulated emotions gradually shape a stable individual memory and common group belief of cooking culture. At the same time, cooking culture continues by generation and to be called tradition.

Through design, form, function, and aesthetics, both internal and external experiences help users establish a stable inner connection with objects. The inner connection is shaped beneath the surface of life and in unnoticed everyday life, which invisibly deepens people's identification on object or tool. The invisible inner connection integrates object, user, environment, tradition into a cultural system which finally constitutes Chinese food and cooking culture. Beyond the utility, this case *fu* (pot) presents deep meaning that possibly is users' memory and emotion on tools or their identifications on group culture. Based on above analysis, it is reasonable to speculate that people maintain the form, function, and design concept because of Chinese psychological and emotion needs on objects (tool).

Conclusion

From a step by step observation, interaction, description and explanation, the inner connection between users and objects is revealed through the case study of the *fu* (pot). From the case, this study shows the design principle which was used in past and present. The study also reveals the reason why the form and function of a case maintained through thousands of years in Chinese history and how the design consistency which exists in four examples was constructed. The case analysis and the application of psychological theory construct a speculation about how objects arouse meaning for users and how Chinese emotion shapes hidden factors in Chinese daily cooking utensils.

According to the interpretation of *fu* (pot), it proves the statement of scholar Gadamer, Hans Georg: “we never know a historical work as it originally appeared to its contemporaries.” Tradition and history is in people's daily living. We have no access to its original context of production or to the intentions of its author. However, tradition is always alive. It is not passive and stifling, but productive and in constant development. The past is handed over to us through the complex and ever-changing fabric of interpretations, which gets richer and more complex as decades and centuries pass.

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